

COVID^X

Three Weeks Left for the #BackToAHealthyFutureEvent

BACK TO A HEALTHY FUTURE

MONTH: SEP DAY: 21-22 YEAR: 2022 DESTINATION: AREA 42, BRUSSELS

NETWORKING OPPORTUNITIES

2-DAY EXHIBITION WITH MORE THAN 40 HEALTHCARE SOLUTIONS

INSPIRATIONAL TALKS

POWERED BY INNO4 COVID-19 COVID^X

ROUNDTABLES: REGULATORY BARRIERS & HEALTHCARE BEST PRACTICES

MORE INFO & REGISTRATION AT: [QR CODE]

Get to know more about the speakers, the companies exhibiting, the roundtables and the matchmaking sessions. Register for the event! Just three weeks left!

[Register](#)

Who is coming to the event?

By registering you can access all the information about the people attending the event, companies exhibiting and the speakers participating in the #BacktoAHealthyFutureEvent.

[Learn more](#)

Matchmaking sessions

Initiate and arrange promising pre-scheduled 1:1 meetings at the event. Generate fresh leads and meet new contacts in a time and cost-efficient way.

[Learn more](#)

ODIN Open Call
420,000€ available for AI
and Big Data solutions
Join us!

→ #ODINopencall

Have a look at our collaborator's Open Call

ODIN's Open Call→Are you an startup, SME, midcap, industry, research centre or technology organization? Get involved in the #ODINopencall, they are looking for entities leading AI, BigData, DataAnalytics in healthcare to join them!

[Open Call](#)

[COVINFORM latest news!](#)

Check the latest news about one of our PREPARE Cluster's collaborators!

COVID-X

www.covid-x.eu / info@covid-x.eu

This document has been prepared by the COVID-X programme. It does not reflect the opinion of any single COVID-X partner or any of the organisations with which the experts are affiliated. The COVID-X programme and its consortium partners are not liable for any consequence stemming from the reuse of this newsletter.

COVID-X has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101016065. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

[Unsubscribe](#)

Sent by
 sendinblue